

The tribe Lychnideae A. Br., 1843 (Caryophyllaceae Juss., 1789) in the flora of Southern Siberia: opportunities and prospects for utilization *

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Abstract

This study explores the biodiversity and biochemical potential of the Lychnideae tribe in Southern Siberia. The region's flora, shaped by extreme environmental conditions, synthesizes unique biologically active compounds with potential therapeutic applications, including anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects. Field studies, herbarium analysis, and literature reviews were conducted to assess species distribution, ecological characteristics, and secondary metabolites. Of the 44 species studied, 19 showed promising use potential, while five require conservation measures. These findings highlight the importance of sustainable resource utilization and biodiversity preservation in pharmacological research.

Keywords

Lychnideae, Southern Siberia, biodiversity, medicinal plants, secondary metabolites, conservation, pharmacology, ecdysteroids, flavonoids, sustainable use

Introduction

In the context of the rapid development of pharmacology, the search for new sources of biologically active compounds, including medicinal plants, has become one

of the priority tasks of modern science. Southern Siberia, with its unique biodiversity and specific climatic conditions, represents a promising region for identifying plants with potentially beneficial properties. The study of the local flora provides access to biologically active substances capable of exerting a wide range of positive effects on human health, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, immunomodulatory, and other effects.

Scientific studies demonstrate that plants growing under extreme conditions – such as sharp temperature fluctuations, limited water availability, and high levels of solar radiation – synthesize specific compounds that enable their adaptation and protection (Yeshi et al. 2022). These substances often exhibit significant biological activity, making them promising candidates for the development of natural products aimed at preventing and treating various diseases. Beyond their medical potential, the study of such plants plays a crucial role in biodiversity conservation and ecosystem resilience. The obtained data on the distribution and beneficial properties of plants can serve as a basis for developing evidence-based strategies that include the sustainable use of plant resources and conservation measures aimed at preventing population degradation and preserving species diversity.

The potential of species of the tribe Lychnideae A. Br., 1843 (Caryophyllaceae Juss., 1789) was first noted during the screening of the flora of the Altai Mountains and has since been repeatedly confirmed by other researchers (Revina et al. 1988; Volodin et al. 2013). These findings underscore the importance of further studies aimed at identifying and investigating the biologically active compounds synthesized by plants of this tribe.

Materials and methods

Southern Siberia was selected as the study area due to its rich and diverse flora. The region of Southern Siberia is bounded by latitudes 49°–57°N and longitudes 65°–120°E, with its boundaries extending approximately 850 km from north to south and nearly 4000 km from west to east.

The study focuses on the tribe Lychnideae of the family Caryophyllaceae, which has garnered significant attention from researchers due to its high biochemical potential. To determine the species composition, distribution, and ecological characteristics of the species, field studies were conducted in the southeastern part of the West Siberian Plain, the Altai Mountains, Khakassia, Tuva, and the Western Sayan Mountains between 2017 and 2023. Herbarium materials from the P.N. Krylov Herbarium of Tomsk State University (TK) and the Herbarium of Moscow State University (MW) were utilized, along with literature data from key floristic works (Shishkin 1936; Kovtonyuk, Zuev 1993; Vlasova 2012; Ebel 2012).

Systematic literature reviews were conducted to search for and analyze data on secondary metabolites of plants, such as ecdysteroids, phenols, flavonoids, and their glycosides. Preference was given to recent publications that utilized screening

data and systematic reviews. In the absence of such studies, results from individual investigations focusing on the identification and characterization of metabolites were considered. The literature search was performed using the PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar databases, enabling the inclusion of studies published between 2000 and 2024 (Zibareva 2000, 2009; Ramazonov et al. 2007; Bajpai et al. 2008; Munkhzhargal et al. 2010; Smolyakova et al. 2010; Darmogray et al. 2015; Novozhilova et al. 2015; Plotnikov et al. 2017; Olennikov 2019; Darmogray et al. 2017; Kozhanova et al. 2020; Zibareva et al. 2022; Smakosz et al. 2024).

To evaluate the potential of each species as a source of biologically active compounds, the following criteria were considered: habitat range, frequency of occurrence, abundance, and the feasibility of introduction under cultivated conditions. The analysis of plant potential was carried out using the algorithm proposed by A.S. Revushkin (Revushkin et al. 2023).

Results

In Southern Siberia, the tribe Lychnideae comprises 44 species belonging to 10 genera: *Agrostemma* L., 1753 (1), *Coccyganthe* Rchb., 1844 (1), *Elisanthe* (Fenzl ex Endl.) Rchb., 1841 (4), *Gastrolychnis* (Fenzl) Rchb., 1841 (6), *Lychnis* L., 1753 (3), *Melandrium* Röhl., 1812 (2), *Oberna* Adans., 1763 (2), *Otites* Adans., 1763 (6), *Silene* L., 1753 (18), and *Steris* Adans., 1763 (1).

Using the proposed algorithm, four groups of plants with varying potential for use were identified:

1. Economically harmful species.
2. Promising species for use:
 - 2a – Species with the potential for their use from natural resources;
 - 2b – Species with the potential for introduction;
 - 2c – Species that require tissue culture.
3. Species of little promise and unpromising species.
4. Species that require special conservation measures.

Economically harmful plants. This group does not include plants from the tribe Lychnideae. However, it is worth noting that *Agrostemma githago* L. 1753 previously posed challenges for agriculture due to its toxicity, caused by the presence of gipsogenin, and its tendency to act as a weed in crops (Nadezhkin 2010). Modern agricultural technologies have minimized this threat, and therefore, this species is not included in the first group.

Plants with promising potential for use. This group includes 19 species, accounting for 42.2% of the total composition of the tribe. Although species of the tribe Lychnideae are not utilized in officinal medicine and are not listed in the pharmacopoeial registers of the Russian Federation (Shikov et al. 2021), many of them have a long history of use in folk and traditional medicine. For instance, *Coccyganthe flos-cuculi* (L.) Fourr. 1844, *Elisanthe firma* (Siebold & Zucc.) Devyatov

& V.N.Tikhom., 1992, *Melandrium album* (Mill.) Garcke, 1858, *Oberna behen* (L.) Ikonn., 1976, and *Silene jeniseensis* Willd., 1809 have traditionally been used to treat various ailments (Chandra and Rawat 2015; Taldybay et al. 2024).

Group 2a (species with the potential for their use from natural resources) includes 12 plant species, accounting for 15.6% of the tribe's composition. This group comprises the following species: *Agrostemma githago*, *Coccyganthe flos-cuculi*, *Elisanthe noctiflora* (L.) Rupr., 1860, *Lychnis chalconica* L., 1753, *Melandrium album*, *M. dioicum* (L.) Coss. & Germ., 1845, *Oberna behen*, *Silene amoena* L., 1753, *S. chlorantha* (Willd.) Ehrh., 1792, *S. graminifolia* Otth., 1824, *S. jenisseensis*, *S. nutans* L., 1753.

Species included in Group 2b (species with potential for introduction) represent 15.6% of the studied taxa. This group comprises *Elisanthe firma*, *Otites parviflorus* (Ehrh.) Grossh., 1868, *O. wolgensis* (Hornem.) Grossh., 1945, *Silene armeria* L. 1753, *S. dichotoma* Ehrh. 1792, as well as two species listed in regional Red Books: *E. viscosa* (L.) Rupr., 1869 (Red Data Book of Tomsk Region 2023) and *S. sibirica* (L.) Pers., 1805 (Red Data Book of Tyumen Region 2020). These Red-listed species are documented only within the specified regions; however, they are also found beyond these areas, making their seeds viable for further introduction into other regions. The introduction of these species may facilitate their adaptation to new environments and contribute to their sustainable existence and conservation.

Group 2c (species that require tissue culture) does not include any species from the tribe, as their seed productivity and germination capacity make them suitable for use as introduction candidates, rendering this category impractical for the studied taxa. Nevertheless, the application of bioengineering approaches and modeling of extreme conditions represent promising directions that could significantly enhance the synthesis of secondary metabolites (Thakur et al. 2019). This approach is particularly relevant for plants growing in mountainous, arid, or saline regions of Southern Siberia.

Species of little promise and unpromising species. This group comprises slightly less than half of the species in the tribe Lychnideae – 21 species (46.7%) – and includes plants that have been insufficiently or not at all studied for their secondary metabolite content. However, this does not rule out their potential value. The group includes: *Elisanthe aprica* (Turcz.) Peschkova, 1979, *Gastrolychnis brachypetala* (Hornem.) Tolm. & Kozhanch., 1971, *G. gracilis* (Tolm.) Czerep., 1981, *G. saxatilis* (Turcz. ex Fisch. & C.A.Mey.) Peschkova, 1979, *G. uniflora* (Ledeb.) Tzvel-ev, 2000, *Lychnis sibirica* L., 1753, *Oberna procumbens* Murr., 1976, *Otites baschkiroorum* (Janisch.) Holub, 1970, *O. exaltatus* (Friv.) Holub, 1970, *O. jenissensis* Klovov, 1974, *O. medius* (Litv.) Klovov, 1948, *Silene chamarensis* Turcz., 1842, *S. fruticulosa* Bieb., 1798, *S. intramongolica* Lazkov, 1999, *S. multiflora* (Ehrh.) Pers., 1805, *S. stylosa* Bunge, 1830, *S. turgida* Bieb. ex Bunge, 1835, *S. turczaninovii* Lazkov, 1999, *S. zuntoreica* Zuev, 1993, *Steris viscaria* (L.) Raf., 1840.

Species that require special conservation measures. This group includes 5 species (11.1%) that are endangered and require conservation measures: *Gastrolychnis*

popovii Peschkova 1975 (Red Data Book of the Republic of Buryatia 2013), *G. tristis* (Bunge) Czerep., 1981 (Red Data Book of Altai Krai 2016; Red Data Book of Kuzbass 2021), *Lychnis fulgens* Fischer 1819 (Red Data Book of the Transbaikal Territory 2016), *Silene altaica* Pers. 1805 (Red Data Book of Altai Krai 2016), *S. incurvifolia* Kar. et Kir., 1841 (Red Data Book of Altai Krai 2016).

Conclusion

The study of plants from the tribe Lychnideae of the family Caryophyllaceae, growing in the conditions of Southern Siberia, confirms their significant potential as sources of biologically active compounds, including ecdysteroids, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds. Analysis of the species composition, distribution, and ecological characteristics allowed the identification of promising species for natural resource utilization, introduction, and tissue culture development. Special attention should be given to species requiring protection due to their rarity and high importance for preserving the region's biodiversity. The findings underscore the importance of further research aimed at identifying and studying secondary metabolites, opening new opportunities for the development of natural preparations with a wide range of pharmacological activities.

References

- Bajpai VK, Shukla S, Kang SC (2008) Chemical composition and antifungal activity of essential oil and various extract of *Silene armeria* L. Bioresource technology 99(18): 8903–8908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2008.04.060>
- Chandra S, Rawat DS (2015) Medicinal plants of the family Caryophyllaceae: a review of ethno-medicinal uses and pharmacological properties. Integrative medicine research 4(3): 123–131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imr.2015.06.004>
- Darmogray VN, Erofeeva NS, Darmogray SV, Filippova AS, Morozova VA, Dubodelova GV (2015) Qualitative and quantitative determination of ecdysteroids and polyphenolic compounds in the herb of *Otites parviflorus* Grossh. Advances in current natural sciences 12: 21–25. [In Russian]
- Darmogray SV, Erofeeva NS, Filippova AS, Dubodelova GV, Morozova VA, Darmogray VN (2017) Chemotaxonomic study of some species of the Caryophyllaceae Juss. family, belonging to different subfamilies. International Journal of Applied and Fundamental Researches (1-2): 287–290. [In Russian]
- Ebel AL (2012) Synopsis of the flora of north-west part of Altay-Sayan province. Irbis, Kemerovo, 566 pp. [In Russian]
- Kovtonyuk NK, Zuev VV (1993) Family Caryophyllaceae. In: Malyshev LI, Peshkova GA (Eds) Flora of Siberia. Volume 6. Nauka, Novosibirsk, 11–95 p. [In Russian]

- Kozhanova AM, Tuleuov BI, Kudabaeva PK, Temirgaziev BS, Seilkhanov TM, Seidakhmetova RB, Salykeeva LK, Adekenov SM (2020) Synthesis, NMR spectroscopic study of α -, β -, and γ -cyclodextrin inclusion complexes of 2-deoxyecdysone and their anti-inflammatory activity. *Macroheterocycles* 13(3): 292–297. [In Russian]
- Munkhzhargal N, Zibareva LN, Lafont R, Pribytkova LN, Pisareva SI (2010) Investigation of ecdysteroid content and composition of *Silene repens* indigenous in Mongolia and introduced into western Siberia. *Russian journal of bioorganic chemistry* 36: 923–928. [In Russian]
- Nadezhkin SN, Kuznetsov IY (2010) Useful, harmful, and poisonous plants: a reference book. KnoRus, Moscow, 248 pp. [In Russian]
- Novozhilova E, Rybin V, Gorovoy P, Gavrilenko I, Doudkin R (2015) Phytoecdysteroids of the East Asian *Caryophyllaceae*. *Pharmacognosy Magazine* 11(Suppl 1): S225. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0973-1296.157746>
- Oleznikov DN (2019) Ecdysteroids, flavonoids, and phenylpropanoids from *Silene nutans*. *Chemistry of Natural Compounds* 55: 127–130. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10600-019-02632-8>
- Plotnikov M, Zibareva L, Vasilev A, Aliev O (2017) An Extract of *Lychnis chalconica* as the Basis for Developing a Novel Ecdysteroid-Containing Formulation with Actoprotector Activity. *Pharmaceutical Chemistry Journal* 51: 800–805. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11094-017-1696-y>
- Ramazonov NS, Mamadalieva NZ, Bobaev ID (2007) Phytoecdysteroids from five species of the genus *Silene*. *Chemistry of Natural Compounds* 43(1): 117–118. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10600-007-0049-6>
- Red Data Book of Altai Krai (2016) Volume 1. Altai State University Publishing House, Barnaul, 292 pp.
- Red Data Book of Kuzbass (2021) Third edition. VEKTOR-PRINT, Kemerovo, 240 pp. [In Russian]
- Red Data Book of the Republic of Buryatia (2013) Rare and endangered species of animals, plants, and fungi. Third edition. Publishing House of the Buryat Scientific Center SB RAS, Ulan-Ude, 687 pp. [In Russian]
- Red Data Book of the Transbaikal Territory (2017) Plants. Dom Mira, Novosibirsk, 366 pp. [In Russian]
- Red Data Book of Tomsk Region (2023) Third edition. Protsvet, Tomsk, Elista, 579 pp. [In Russian]
- Red Data Book of Tyumen Region (2020) Third edition. Technoprint, Kemerovo, 460 pp. [In Russian]
- Revina TA, Revushkin AS, Rakitin AV (1988) Ecdysteroid-containing species in the flora of the Altai Mountains. *Plant resources* 4: 565–569. [In Russian]
- Revushkin AS, Kasterova EA, Chigodaikina DS, Zibareva LN (2023) Search for new sources of bioactive compounds in the flora of Southern Siberia and evaluation of the potential for their use. *Acta Biologica Sibirica* 9: 23–34. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7679976>

- Shikov AN, Narkevich IA, Flisyuk EV, Luzhanin VG, Pozharitskaya ON (2021) Medicinal plants from the 14th edition of the Russian Pharmacopoeia, recent updates. *Journal of ethnopharmacology* 268: 113685. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2020.113685>
- Shishkin BK (1936) Fam. LX. Caryophyllaceae Juss. In: Shishkin BK (Ed.) *Flora of the USSR*. Publishing House of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR, Moscow, Leningrad, 394–870 p. [In Russian]
- Smakosz A, Matkowski A, Nawrot-Hadzik I (2024) Phytochemistry and Biological Activities of *Agrostemma* Genus – A Review. *Plants* 13(12): 1673. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants13121673>
- Smolyakova IM, Avdeenko SN, Kalinkina G, Yusubov MS, Zibareva LN (2010) Study of the chemical composition of *Lychnis chalconica*, cultivated in Western Siberia. Part II. HPLC chromatographic study of phenolic compounds and ecdysteroids of *Lychnis chalconica*, cultivated in Western Siberia. *Chemistry of Plant Raw Materials* (3): 95–102. [In Russian]
- Taldybay A, Aidarbayeva D, Kurmantayeva A, Mussaev K, Amanbekova D, Joltukova B (2024) Medicinal plants in the flora of Zhetysu Alatau, Zhetysu Region, Kazakhstan. *Caspian Journal of Environmental Sciences* 22(3): 567–579.
- Thakur M, Bhattacharya S, Khosla PK, Puri S (2019) Improving production of plant secondary metabolites through biotic and abiotic elicitation. *Journal of Applied Research on Medicinal and Aromatic Plants* 12: 1–12. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jarmap.2018.11.004>
- Vlasova NV (2012) Family Caryophyllaceae Juss. In: Baikov KS (Ed.) *Conspectus Florae Asiaticae Russiae: Vascular Plants*. Publishing House of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Novosibirsk, 69–91 p. [In Russian]
- Volodin VV, Shadrin DM, Pylina YI, Druz YI, Volodina SO, Chadin IF, Dainan L (2013) Molecular phylogeny and chemotaxonomy of ecdysteroid-containing plants of the families Caryophyllaceae Juss. and Asteraceae Dumort. *Bulletin of Biotechnology and Physical and Chemical Biology named after Yu.A. Ovchinnikov* 9(1): 21–27. [In Russian]
- Yeshi K, Crayn D, Ritmejeriyé E, Wangchuk P (2022) Plant Secondary Metabolites Produced in Response to Abiotic Stresses Has Potential Application in Pharmaceutical Product Development. *Molecules* 27(1): 1–31. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27010313>
- Zibareva L (2000) Distribution and levels of phytoecdysteroids in plants of the genus *Silene* during development. *Archives of Insect Biochemistry and Physiology* 43(1): 1–8.
- Zibareva LN (2009) Phytoecdysteroids of Caryophyllaceae Juss. *Contemporary Problems of Ecology* 2(5): 476–488. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1134/S1995425509050154>
- Zibareva LN, Filonenko ES, Chernyak E, Morozov SV, Kotelnikov OA (2022) Flavonoids of some species of the *Silene* genus. *Chemistry of Plant Raw Materials* (3): 109–118. [In Russian]